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A STUDY ON CASCADING IMPACT OF DEMONETIZATION ON LIVELIHOOD IN BELGAUM CITY OF KARNATAKA

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ABSTRACT

Demonetization has often been used as a tool to cut down hyper inflation. Which is essential to maintain country inflation in a moderate level in turn helps to have fastest growing economy in the world? Prime Minister of India Mr. Narendra Modi came out with his master stroke on corruption, counterfeit currency, terrorism and black money by announcing demonetization and ceasing Rs 500 and Rs. 1000 notes as a part of legal tender in India. Many of the scholars, politicians, business men and every other category the society defined their views in different way about the effects of demonetization in India. Hence this study has been taken up to know the reality of the Cascading impact of this demonetization on livelihoods of the Belgaum city of Karnataka. Emphasis was given on studying the various factors and problems / constraints faced by the people by the Demonetization in Belgaum city of Karnataka. Primary data was collected by taking response of different class of the people in Belgaum city of Karnataka with help of structured questionnaire. Secondary data was elicited from different websites and journals and Newspaper for the study and the data collected was analyzed by using the statistical tools like Frequencies and percentage.

The overall results revealed that the impact of demonetization was almost on positive rather than Negative impact on livelihood of the study area.

Key words: Cascading, Demonitization, Livelihood, Karnataka.

Introduction

The term demonetization has become a household name since the government pulled the old Rs 500 and Rs 1,000 notes out of circulation. While as per dictionary demonetization means "ending something (e.g. gold or silver) that is no longer the legal tender of a country". When a currency note of a particular denomination ceases to be a legal tender it is termed as demonetization. But since our government is replacing the old Rs 500 notes with newer ones and doing away with the Rs 1,000 notes, it would be more appropriate to call the move as `scrapping' or `phasing out' of certain currency notes

Demonetization has often been used as a tool to cut down **hyper inflation**. Which ie essential to maintain country inflation in a moderate level in turn helps to have fastest growing economy in the world.

The term demonetization is not new to the Indian economy. The highest denomination note ever printed by the Reserve Bank of India was the Rs 10,000 note in 1938 and again in 1954. But these notes were demonetized in January 1946 and again in January 1978, according to RBI data

Prime Minister of India, Mr Narendra Modi, took the entire country by surprise when he declared demonetization of INR 500/- (USD 7.69) and INR 1,000/- (USD 15.4) currency on 8th November, 2016. As per Modi Government, the agenda of this move with following three objectives

1. To eliminate counterfeit currency;
2. To shrink the size of the parallel economy and black money in India; and
3. To reduce corruption.

While this is the third time in the Indian history that Indian high value currency has been stripped of its status as a legal tender, the first two instances of demonetization did not have an impact like the recent one. This is primarily because, this time, the demonetized currency represents 86% of the total currency in circulation. In a country where 68% of the transaction are cash based (as per CLSA i.e. Credit Lyonnais Securities Asia data), a move like this is definitely going to have several long- as well as short-term impacts.

On November 8 2016, when the whole world was waiting for the outcome of US presidential elections, Prime Minister Narendra Modi came out with his master stroke on corruption, counterfeit currency, terrorism and black money by announcing demonetization and ceasing Rs 500 and Rs. 1000 notes as a part of legal tender in India.

The Reserve Bank of India manages currency in India and derives its role in currency management on the basis of the Reserve Bank of India Act, 1934 and a new redesigned series of Rs 500 banknote, in addition to a new denomination of Rs 2000 banknote is in circulation since November 10, 2016. The new redesigned series is also expected to be introduced to the banknote denominations of Rs 1000, Rs 100 and Rs 50 in the coming months.

However, with the latest round of demonetization, the common public and bankers are undoubtedly facing hardship since more than 85 percent of currency in circulation has been rendered illegal in one single stroke. Demonetization is surely hampering the current economy and will continue to do so in the near term and will also impact India's growth for the coming two quarters but will have positive long lasting effects. The question that arises is why demonetization was required at this point of time. There are certain pros and cons of demonetization.

Pros

One of the biggest advantage of this demonetization act is to drastically affect the corrupt practices. People who are holding black money in cash will not be able to exchange much as they would be in a fear of getting penalized and prosecuted by the authorities. Enemies of the country which are involved in counterfeit currency and terrorism will not be able to continue it further for quite some time at least and the smuggling of arms and dealing with the terrorist will not sustain further as all of the money will be on record now.

Secondly, the banking system will improve as it will slowly head towards a cashless society. Cashless society will increase credit access and financial inclusion. The existing white money of people will be known to the government and it will remain with banks so that it can be put on loan, and interest can be generated from it (though interest rates would fall) with a corresponding fall in Inflation.

Further Banking System will get a boost, as more than Rs 7-8 lakh crore base money (new legal money) will enter the system. However, it needs to be seen how much money actually remains in the system, once the cash withdrawal limits are eased.

Thirdly, it will reduce the risk and cost of cash handling as soft money is safer than hard money. It will also reduce government liability. Since every note is a liability for the government, the old currency will become worthless for those people, who choose not to disclose their income. Thus, this will extinguish government's liability to that extent. It is expected approximately Rs 5 lakh crore may come to the government in the form of extinguished RBI liability, taxes and penalties. This amount is enough to take care of India's entire fiscal deficit for one year or more.

It will also reduce tax avoidance. Whatever money will be deposited or exchanged, authorities will keep a track of it and they will be extra cautious in this period. Dealing in this period in sectors like jewellery and real estate will be on radar and those entering into Loan transactions may also undergo tax scrutiny. Search and Seizure

activities of the IT Department will also rise to curb such malpractices. Limits have already been prescribed for reporting to the IT Department those bank accounts in which excess cash deposits are being made in this 50-day window (Rs 2.5 lakh in case of individuals and Rs 12.5 lakh in case of firms).

Importantly, in the longer run, tax and interest rates on loans are expected to come down as higher income tax collections arising from better compliance would offer scope to reduce rates over the long term. This, in turn, will drive up disposable income. This can give a positive impact on consumption demand in long term.

Cons

The liquidity squeeze caused by demonetization will be negative across sectors with high level of cash transactions. Real estate, jewellery, retailing, restaurants, logistics, consumer durables and luxury brands, cement and some segments in retail/SME lending space will be facing short term instability. Those companies with high level of debt will face more pressure and can face loan defaults.

Secondly, there will be added replacement costs of currency. We cannot ignore the increased cost of operating ATMs need to be refilled more often and also it will be a huge burden on banks. Initially, it is very difficult to create a cashless society as more than 50 percent of Indian population is not well versed with card transactions. Also for these initial months, it will be very difficult to make cash transactions of a higher amount. But the government is taking steps to improve liquidity into the system and reduce inconvenience as much as possible.

India is certainly going to experience "**Acche Din**" in Modi's regime. The decision of this surgical strike on black money was not taken in a day or two. Rome was not built in a day and similarly, this plan is the result of Prime Minister's meticulous planning and never ending fight against corruption. As a result, he has successfully made the right stroke at the right time.

Further, the penal provisions are hefty enough to ensure that corrupt practices will find it hard to take roots again. Despite certain short term troubles, demonetization is certainly going to give a boost to the Indian economy in the long run.

Views from Eminent Personalities about move of demonetization in India

A. Experts and Economists who are against Demonetization

1. Amartya Sen: Leading economist; Noble Laureate; recipient of the Bharat Ratna

Calls the move authoritarian: Professor Sen said, "Only an authoritarian government can calmly cause such misery to the people — with millions of innocent people being deprived of their money and being subjected to suffering, inconvenience and indignity in trying to get their own money back.

2. Dr. Manmohan Singh: Former Prime Minister; eminent economist; former RBI governor

Overall opinion: Speaking at the Rajya Sabha, Dr. Singh has called demonetisation an "organised loot" , a "legalised plunder" and a "monumental mismanagement". He even said that the National income would fall by 2 per cent, which in his mind was "an underestimate"

3. Kaushik Basu: Leading economist; Senior Vice-President and Chief Economist at The World Bank

Cannot wipe out black money; hoarders have already found loopholes: "Anyone seeking to convert more than Rs 250,000 must explain why they hold so much cash, or failing that, must pay a penalty," Large amounts of illicit cash are broken into smaller blocks and deposited by teams of illegal couriers"

4. Arun Shourie: Former economist at the World Bank; recipient of the Padma Bhushan and Union Minister

If the government was planning this for months, how could it be possibly so ill-prepared? Shourie said government could not anticipate any problems when they finish off 85 percent of the currency value in India.

"Small and medium enterprises, transport sector, the entire agricultural sector—I can't reach them. I can't reach 6 lakh villages. They did not think about this?"

B. Experts and Economists who are for Demonetization:

1. Arun Jaitley: Current Finance Minister of India; Senior Advocate, Delhi High Court

Eventually, the government will be able to invest more money in agriculture and social sector: "A lot of money that operates in the shadow economy will now become a part of the banking structure itself. Banks will have a lot more money to support the economy. Private sector investment, which was so far lacking, will now get back into the economy. The banks which were struggling because of the NPA problem will have a lot more money to lend for agriculture, infrastructure sector, social sector, trade and industry."

2. Arvind Virmani: Leading economist; Former India's representative at IMF; Former Chief Economic Adviser, GOI

Useful method; secrecy was a per-requisite: "This is a useful method of flushing out black money, given that a large percentage of cash holding is in these two denominations. The manner in which it was implemented is not surprising – such actions are always secret till announced, so that insiders do not take advantage of the information at the cost of the outsiders,

3. Adi Godrej. The Chairman of the Godrej group

Demonetization may have had "considerable negative effect" in the first few days but the situation now has improved and it will have a positive impact on the economy, leading industrialist Adi Godrej has said. The Chairman of the Godrej group also welcomed the step saying it would help combat black money and reduce corruption, while having a positive result on the economic front. "As far as the effect on the economy is concerned, it will have a considerable negative effect in the first few days after the policy was announced in November. But since then the situation has improved quite considerably and we are seeing a strong pick up in demand of many of our products now,"

He further said there is a fair amount of cash injected into the economy and more is being injected regularly. "So I expect a very quick tick up on the economic front also." When asked whether demonetization has hit rural sales, which was expecting a good season riding on good monsoon this year, Godrej said, "Of course, it would dampen the sales but it's catching up very soon. Whatever the stocks were reduced at retailer's end will be replenished very soon. December would be a good month."

Disagreeing with the opponents of demonetization, he said: "A lot of the criticism to my mind is political criticism because the politicians have been hurt." Commenting on GST, he said the Centre needs to take steps to resolve issues with states for its implementation from April 1 next year. "The government should talk to state governments and resolve the issues to implement it. The industry is waiting for it,"

But I spied the Demonization in the following way

The positive impact on Indian economy due to currency ban.

Grocery/vegetable shops: Almost every local grocery vendor in India accepts cash currencies. So naturally they won't be accepting these two currency notes. And this has been noticed right from day 1. No one is ready to accept the currencies except Rs. 100 and lower denominations. So anyone buying grocery will have to either buy them on credit or give small denominations.

Transportation: We all use some form of transportation everyday mainly – auto rickshaw, taxi, buses, cycle rickshaw. All this business will be hit for a day or two especially those who commute longer distances and payment amount is above Rs. 500. So either commuter has to provide smaller denominations or else do not travel or look for some other alternative. Because no one will accept these two most used currency notes.

Truck transport: Almost every business is some way or the other dependent on transportation especially trucks. All drivers and middleman have preferred only cash. No credit card/online transfer etc. They will be impacted badly unless and until they are paid in lower denominations.

Hotels/Restaurants: These businesses will also suffer especially those who accept only cash currencies. No lower currency means no visit to hotel by the customers.

Stock market: Anyone buying/selling physical shares typically pays via cash. In normal scenarios, trading amount is always bigger in quantity and there is no alternative other than paying through lower denominations.

Medical shops: Medicines are lifelines for the patients. Non-availability of lower denominations or non-acceptance of Rs. 500 & 1000 currency notes will result in either medicines bought on credit/lower denominations or not bought at all due to the ban. Not everyone has Rs. 100 and Rs. 50 or lower currency notes in sufficient quantity.

Hospitals: This certainly apart from medical shops will be badly impacted. Patients who are already hospitalized or are under process of getting hospitalized must have done some form of arrangements for money before 08 Nov 2016. They would be badly suffer.

Real estate: This market will be the most badly impacted obviously due to black and white money which have been functional since years. Buyer normally pays certain % of money (black money) in cash to the builder/agents and remaining portion is paid via loan. So any deal of the house which was supposed to happen on 09 Nov, 2016 or even after this date will suffer. Because the black money or brokerage paid to agents involve large sum and all paid in cash. So buyer will either have to re-decide on buying the house or home builder or agent will have to accept these banned notes at their own risk. Or buyer will have to arrange lower denominations and then pay.

Ecommerce industry: Although ecommerce is growing at phenomenal rate in India, mode of payments used by Indians is largely cash on delivery. Because of this decision, their sales will slow down. So this will directly impact businesses of mobile phone companies, clothings, and jewelry especially as they contribute to bigger chunk of online ecommerce market places.

Insurance industry: Online transactions for buying insurance is on rise but still higher number of policies are sold offline. Since normal policy premiums are higher in amount, policies won't be sold offline by most of the companies. So those who are not ready to buy online will buy either at a later date or purchase using lower denominations.

There are numerous businesses such as travel agents, ticket booking agents & many others will take a hit.

Impact on Banks Deposit and Interest Rates - Positive

The growth in Bank deposits, which was at a 53 year low at the end of March 2016, has seen a spike ever since the demonetization was announced in India. The total deposits collected by banks amounted to Rs 6 trillion (~USD 92bn) by 23rd of November 2016. With this rate of money deposited, entire INR 15 trillion (~USD230 bn) of currency demonetized is expected to be deposited by end of December 2016. If most of these deposits being made in the banks are emergency savings of households, most of these deposits will be withdrawn after government uplifts the withdrawal limit.

Hence the Study has been designed to assess the cascading impact of the Demonetization on livelihood in Belgaum city of Karnataka with the following Objectives

1. To study the level of positive/Negative impact of Demonetization in study area
2. To Assess the problems encountered by the public after Demonetization in their commercial activities
3. To Document the Various Issues caused during the Demonetization Period by the Public of the Study Area.

Research Methodology

Descriptive research design was adopted for the study considering the nature and scope of the study. Emphasis was given on studying the various factors and problems / constraints faced by the people by the Demonetization in Belgaum city of Karnataka. Primary data was collected by taking response of different class of the people in Belgaum city of Karnataka with help of structured questionnaire. Secondary data was elicited from different websites and journals and Newspaper for the study. And the data was collected from totally 100 respondents i.e. 25 each from Students, Government employees. Public (less than 60 years) and Senior Citizens (more than 60 years age) respectively

The data collected was analyzed by using the statistical tools like Frequencies and percentage.

Results and Discussion

Table 1: Ranking of problems by sample Respondents

Sl. No.	Descripti on problem	Max. Score point	Students			Govt. Employees			Public (less than 60 Years age)			Senior citizens (more than 60 Years age)		
			Avg. No persons Scored problem	% of points scored	Rank of problem	Avg. No persons Scored problem	% of points scored	Rank of problem	Avg. No persons Scored problem	% of points scored	Rank of problem	Avg. No persons Scored problem	% of points scored	Rank of problem
1.	Women Security	25	01	4	V	03	12	IV	02	8	III	01	04	V
2.	Black Money	25	12	48	I	07	28	I	07	28	I	12	48	I
3.	Terrorism , Poverty	25	05	20	II	03	12	IV	06	24	II	05	20	II
4.	Unemplo yment	25	01	4	V	01	4	VI	01	4	IV	01	04	V
5	Fake currency	25	03	12	III	04	16	III	06	24	II	03	12	III
6	Corruptio n	25	02	8	IV	05	20	II	02	08	III	02	08	IV
7	Inequitabl e Distributi on of Income	25	01	4	V	02	8	V	01	04	IV	01	04	V

In order to analyse the problems faced by the sample respondents regarding demonetization, a set of questionnaire was developed in order to document the problems faced by the units and their suggestions towards stated problems. The suggestions and opinions were culled out to ascertain the major problems affecting livelihood of the civilians of the Belgaum City of Karnataka.

The list of various problems faced by the country i.e India, their respective scores and ranking were given in Table 1.

The four Categories of the respondent's viz., **Students, Govt. Employees, Public (less than 60 Years age) and Senior citizens (more than 60 Years age)** considered for the study faced similar kinds of problems, but the extent of severity varied from category to category of the people so the each category is asked to rank the problems viz., Women Security, Black Money, Terrorism, Poverty, Unemployment, Fake currency, Corruption and Inequitable Distribution of Income.

In Students category, Black Money, Terrorism, Poverty, and Fake currency were identified as major problems, which scored I, II, and III Rank respectively.

With respect to Government Employees, the major problems identified are Black Money, Corruption and Fake currency Ranked as I, II and III ranks respectively.

In the case of Public (less than 60 Years age), Black Money, Terrorism, Poverty and Corruption are the major problems rated as I, II and III ranks respectively.

Similarly, in the **Senior citizens (more than 60 Years age) group** identified the major problems are Black Money, Terrorism, Poverty and Fake currency are ranked as I, II and III respectively.

Table 2: Percentage Affected by Demonetization Process in Study Area.

Particulars	Students	Govt. Employees	Public (less than 60 Years)	Senior citizens (more than 60 Years)
Rich	92	85	95	90
Middle class	07	17	04	05
Poor	01	08	01	05

The results revealed that regarding percentage affected by Demonetization process in study area (presented in Table 2) in Students category of respondents perceived that nearly 92 % of Rich affected as compared to Middle class 07 % and poor 01 % and among the Government employees category they felt that 85% demonetization affected the Rich followed by Middle class 17% and Poor class 08 %.

Whereas in Public (less than 60Years age) perceived that the demonetization process affected nearly 95 % for the rich class people and 04 percent for Middle class and rest 1% for poor class.

And the results revealed that in case of Senior citizens (more than 60 Years) the demonetization process nearly 90 % affected Rich class and 05 percent affected Middle class and 05 percent for poor class.

Table 3: Average Frequency of Visit to banks for withdrawing money

Particulars	Students	Govt. Employees	Public (less than 60 Years)	Senior citizens (more than 60 Years)
Before 8 th November 2016	3	4	5	3
After 8 th November 2016	2	2	2	2

A careful examination of Table 3 reveals that, before Demonetization Period i.e. before 8th November 2016 the average Frequency of visit to banks for withdrawing money as follows i.e. 3 times by both students and senior Citizens and 4 times per month by Government employees and 5 times per month by general Public (less than 60 years)

Whereas in post Demonetization period i.e. after 8th November 2016, an average nearly all category of the respondents visited two Times Bank for withdrawing cash from their accounts.

Table 4: Perception about Modi Government Move on Banning of Rs 500 and Rs 1000 Notes

Particulars	Students	Govt. Employees	Public (less than 60 Years)	Senior citizens (more than 60 Years)
Very Bad	01	01	03	07
Bad	01	03	02	06
Good	04	05	02	05
Very Good	19	16	18	07

The Perception about Modi Government Move on Banning of Rs 500 and Rs 1000 Notes are presented in Table 4 and the results revealed that the majority of the respondents opined that the move is very good i.e about 19 % in students category and 16 % form Government employees and 18 percent form General public (Less than 60 Years) and nearly 07 % form senior Citizens (More than 60 Years).

Table 5: Perception about wastage of time in banks is justified to minimize terrorism

Particulars	Students	Govt. Employees	Public (less than 60 Years)	Senior citizens (more than 60 Years)
Strongly Disagree	02	01	00	12
Disagree	00	02	00	04
Neutral	03	04	02	06
Agree	09	17	18	06
Strongly agree	85	75	80	72

The Perception about wastage of time in banks is justified to minimize terrorism is presented in Table 5 and the results showed that majority of the respondents felt that nearly 72 to 85 percent perceived that strongly agree by Senior Citizens and Students respectively about this and meager percent opined as Strongly Dis agree for this act.

Table 6: Government Demonetization move is politically motivated

Particulars	Overall Percentage
Strongly Dis agree	78
Disagree	12
Neutral	07
Agree	02
Strongly agree	01

The results showed that regarding Government Demonetization move is politically motivated (presented in Table 6) nearly 78 percent of the respondents opined that Strongly Disagree followed by 12 percent , for Disagree and 07 percent are neutral, 02 percent felt as Agree and rest 01 percent gave answer as Strongly Agree.

Table 7: My liquidity position has been seriously affected by Demonetization

Particulars	Overall Percentage
Strongly Dis agree	80
Disagree	12
Neutral	05
Agree	03
Strongly agree	01

Table 7 represents the opinions regarding the extent of respondent’s liquidity position affected by this Demonetization process. And it was observed that 80 percent of the respondents felt they are strongly Disagree followed by 12 percent, 05 percent,03 percent and 01 percent as Disagree, Neutral , agree and Strongly Agree respectively

Graph 8 showed the average opinions of the sample respondents towards Government move to release Rs 2000 notes will not help/help in curbing the corruption. The results showed that the nearly 68 percent of the respondents opined strongly Disagree and about 08 percent felt as strongly Agree.

Table 9: New Rs 2000 notes can be easily misused by Terrorists.

The results revealed that regarding the New Rs 2000 notes can be easily misused by Terrorist are presented in Table 9, the results inferred that nearly 82 percent perceived as Strongly agree and 2 percent of the respondents gave answer as strongly Disagree

Table 10: Banks and ATMs do not offer sufficient cash to their customers.

Graph 10 showed the average percentage of the sample respondent's opinions regarding the Banks and ATMs do not offer sufficient cash to their customers. And the study backed the results as nearly majority i.e. 58 percent are opined as Agree and 12 percent felt as both Strongly Agree and Strongly Disagree and 14 percent felt as disagree and rest 4 percent landed as neutral

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